

WAYS OF ENHANCING POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS' POLYCULTURAL COMPETENCE THROUGH PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS

Kuysin Tukhtaeva

Associate professor of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute
Navoi, Uzbekistan
kuysin.tukhtaeva1961@gmail.com
+998973436566

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12541358>

Annotation: The article is devoted to the problems of enhancing postgraduate students' polycultural competence through paremiological units. It gives definition the paremias and enumerates types of them according to the formation of them.

Key words: proverbs, aphorisms, maxims, parables, sayings, mottoes.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена проблемам повышения поликультурной компетентности аспирантов через паремиологические единицы. Дается определение паремий, и перечисляются их виды по формированию.

Ключевые слова: пословицы, афоризмы, изречения, притчи, поговорки, девизы.

Annotatsiya: Maqola paremiologik birliklar orqali aspirantlarning ko'p madaniyatli kompetentsiyasini oshirish muammolariga bag'ishlangan. Maqollarga ta'rif berilib, shakllanishiga ko'ra turlari sanab o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqol, aforizm, matal, matal, matal, shior.

Paremiology is the study of proverbs, or short, popular sayings that express traditional wisdom or common truths. Proverbs are often used to convey advice, moral lessons, or reflections on human behavior in a concise and memorable way. They are found in many cultures and languages around the world and serve as a form of cultural expression and communication.

Paremiological units include such concepts as proverbs, sayings, aphorisms, parables, maxims, sayings, mottoes, etc. Proverbs and sayings are of the greatest interest as stable sayings, which have become the object of research in this article. Paremiology (from Greek παροιμία (paroimía) 'proverb, maxim, saw') is the collection and study of paroemias (proverbs). It is a subfield of both philology and linguistics. An English proverb is a short, pithy statement that usually offers life advice, wisdom, or a truth. Proverbs are so common that native speakers of English may use them in conversation without realizing it. Proverbs can offer a shortcut for explaining or imparting information as well.

Paremiological units, or proverbs, can be classified into different types based on their structure and content. Here are some common types of paremiological units:

- 1. Traditional Proverbs:** These are well-known proverbs that have been passed down through generations and are widely recognized in a particular culture or society.
- 2. Maxims:** Maxims are concise statements of general truth or principle, often offering advice or guidance on how to behave or make decisions.
- 3. Aphorisms:** Aphorisms are short, pithy statements that convey a philosophical or moral idea in a memorable way.
- 4. Adages:** Adages are traditional sayings that offer wisdom or insight into human behavior, often based on observation or experience.
- 5. Epigrams:** Epigrams are witty, clever, or satirical statements that often contain a twist or play on words.
- 6. Folk Sayings:** Folk sayings are proverbs that are specific to a particular region, community, or cultural group.
- 7. Idioms:** Idioms are expressions that have a figurative meaning different from the literal meaning of the words used.
- 8. Quotations:** While not always considered traditional proverbs, famous quotations from literature, speeches, or historical figures can also be studied as paremiological units.

These are just a few examples of the types of paremiological units that exist. Proverbs and sayings come in many forms and serve various purposes in communication and cultural expression. Ways of Enhancing postgraduate students' polycultural competence through paremiological units can be a creative and effective way to promote cross-cultural understanding and communication. Here are some ways this can be achieved:

- 1. Integrating Paremiological Units in Curriculum:** Incorporate proverbs, sayings, and idiomatic expressions from different cultures into the curriculum. Discuss the meanings, origins, and cultural contexts of these expressions to help students understand different cultural perspectives.
- 2. Comparative Analysis:** Encourage students to compare and contrast proverbs from their own culture with those from other cultures. This can help them appreciate the similarities and differences in cultural values and beliefs.
- 3. Interactive Workshops and Activities:** Organize workshops and activities where students can share proverbs from their own cultures, explain their

meanings, and discuss how they relate to everyday life. This interactive approach can foster a deeper understanding of diverse cultural perspectives.

4. Role-Playing Exercises: Use paremiological units in role-playing exercises to simulate real-life cross-cultural interactions. This can help students develop empathy, adaptability, and effective communication skills in multicultural settings.

5. Research Projects: Assign research projects that require students to explore the cultural significance of specific proverbs in different societies. This can deepen their understanding of cultural diversity and enhance their critical thinking skills.

6. Cross-Cultural Communication Training: Provide training on cross-cultural communication strategies, using paremiological units as examples to illustrate how language reflects cultural norms and values.

7. Guest Lectures and Cultural Events: Invite guest speakers from diverse cultural backgrounds to share their insights on the role of proverbs in shaping cultural identities. Organize cultural events that showcase the richness and diversity of world cultures through language and expressions.

Enhancing postgraduate students' polycultural competence is crucial in today's globalized world. Here are some ways to achieve this:

1. Diverse Curriculum: Incorporate diverse perspectives, authors, and case studies into the curriculum to expose students to a wide range of cultural backgrounds and experiences.

2. Intercultural Communication Training: Offer workshops or courses on intercultural communication to help students develop skills in effectively communicating across cultures.

3. Study Abroad Programs: Encourage students to participate in study abroad programs to experience different cultures firsthand and gain a deeper understanding of global issues.

4. Cultural Competency Workshops: Organize workshops that focus on developing cultural competency skills, such as empathy, open-mindedness, and respect for diversity.

5. Collaborative Projects: Assign group projects that require students to work with peers from different cultural backgrounds, promoting collaboration and understanding.

6. Cultural Events and Activities: Organize cultural events, guest lectures, and activities that celebrate diversity and encourage students to engage with different cultures.

7. Mentorship Programs: Pair students with mentors from diverse cultural backgrounds to provide guidance and support in navigating cultural differences.

8. Language Learning Opportunities: Offer language courses or language exchange programs to help students learn new languages and better understand different cultures.

9. Critical Reflection: Encourage students to critically reflect on their own cultural biases and assumptions, challenging them to broaden their perspectives and develop cultural humility.

10. Community Engagement: Engage students in community service or outreach programs that involve working with diverse communities, fostering empathy and understanding.

Implementing these strategies, postgraduate programs can help students develop polycultural competence, enabling them to navigate diverse environments, collaborate effectively with people from different backgrounds, and contribute positively to a multicultural society. By incorporating paremiological units into postgraduate education, educators can empower students to develop a deeper appreciation for cultural diversity, improve their intercultural communication skills, and become more effective global citizens.

References:

1. Usmonova, U. H. qizi, Mukhtorova, B. (2023). Paremiological units of language. *Golden Brain*, 1(1), 241-244. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/goldenbrain/article/view/1190>
2. Musinova, S. H., & Tadjibaev, M. A. (2021). Structural and semantic characteristics of proverbs. *evroaziyskiy soyuz uchenih*, (1-4 (82)), 22-25.
3. Sotvaldieva, K., & Toshmirzayeva, D. (2022). Cognitive study of "happiness" metaphors in english and uzbek idioms. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 914-919.
7. Sotvaldieva, H. M. (2021). Using proverbs as A lead-In activity in teaching english as A Foreign Language. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(11), 159-163.
4. Sotvaldieva, H. M. (2020). English proverbs as a means of expressing people's wisdom, spirit and national mentality. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (2), 601-604.